

[Re] Resampling methods for evaluating classification accuracy of wildlife habitat models

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1 Introduction

Ecological resources are often managed on the basis of outputs derived from models of species-environment relationships, variously referred to as: habitat suitability models, species distribution models, resource selection functions, or ecological niche models. Therefore, evaluating the predictive ability of such models is a necessary prerequisite for robust decision-making. While such evaluations are ideally based on independent data collected purely for the purpose of model testing, in ecological studies fully independent data is often unavailable due to logistical or financial constraints. Therefore, statistical resampling methods are the most important tool we have for evaluating predictive ability.

To briefly summarise, resampling methods repeatedly resample the full dataset to create training and testing data subsets that are independent of one another. The model is then iteratively fit using each training data subset and prediction error estimated using the independent testing data subset. An overall estimate of prediction error is then calculated as the average prediction error across all resampled data subsets. While resampling methods are not a replacement for independent data, they can be used to conduct an internal evaluation that penalises for optimism from overfitting¹.

In their seminal paper on model evaluation Fielding and Bell² state with reference to resampling methods “The ecological literature seems to have paid little attention to how the partitioning method can influence the error rates. Verbyla and Litvaitis briefly reviewed a range of partitioning methods in their assessment of resampling methods for evaluating classification accuracy.” The work of Verbyla and Litvaitis¹ remains the only comparison of resampling methods for evaluating species-environment relationship models. Therefore, given the importance of this work, we endeavoured to replicate the study using an open computational approach.

2 Prediction error

When developing a species-environment relationship model, we will usually have a dataset d that contains observations or measurements that form a species response variable

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Code is available at <https://github.com/tretherington/ReScience-submission/tree/etherington-lieske> – DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3229408.

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y and a set of one or more environmental explanatory variables x . Using a species-environment relationship model function f trained on the dataset $f^{(d)}$ a prediction of the response variable \hat{y} can be created from the environmental explanatory variables for each sample i :

$$\hat{y}_i = f^{(d)}(x_i) \quad (1)$$

We can then define the prediction error Err for each sample i as the absolute difference between the observed response variable y_i and predicted response variable \hat{y}_i :

$$Err_i = |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (2)$$

This definition of Err is equivalent to the binary misclassification error rate used by Verbyla and Litvaitis¹, as when $y_i = \hat{y}$ then $Err_i = 0$, and when $y_i \neq \hat{y}$ then $Err_i = 1$. But by expressing Err in these terms generalises the approach to situations in which the species-environment relationships are measured or modelled on a continuous rather than binary scale, which has become more common practice since the original computational experiment was conducted.

3 Resampling methods

During the replication process it became apparent that the terminology for resampling methods has developed over time, and has been used somewhat inconsistently. Therefore, we begin by naming and formally defining each of the resampling methods we have used based on descriptions within the references.

3.1 Resubstitution

Given a dataset d of size n the resubstitution method calculates the mean prediction error across all samples i from a modelling function trained on the entire dataset $f^{(d)}$.

$$Err^R = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - f^{(d)}(x_i)| \quad (3)$$

The value Err^R is called the resubstitution (or apparent) error rate and is likely to provide an optimistic estimate of prediction error, as the same data is used to train and test the model.

3.2 Hold-out cross-validation

Hold-out (or: split-sample, randomised, Monte Carlo) cross-validation randomly partitions the dataset into training and testing subsets. Verbyla and Litvaitis¹ referred to this approach as simply ‘‘cross-validation’’ but we have chosen to use the more specific term of hold-out cross-validation to clarify which of the many types of cross-validation we are referring to. The proportion p of data ‘held-out’ from the dataset d forms a testing dataset t of sample size $\#t$, with the remaining data forming training dataset $\{d-t\}$. The model is fitted using the training dataset $f^{\{\{d-t\}\}}$, and the prediction error is estimated as the mean prediction error for all i in t across a number of H repetitions.

$$Err_p^H = \frac{1}{H} \sum_{t=1}^H \frac{1}{\#t} \sum_{i \in t} |y_i - f^{\{\{d-t\}\}}(x_i)| \quad (4)$$

In general this method can be considered an improvement over resubstitution as the data used to train the model is separated from the data used to test the model.

3.3 K -fold cross-validation

Verbyla and Litvaitis¹ describe a resampling method called ten-fold cross-validation and another method called n -fold cross-validation or the jackknife. Both these methods are variations of K -fold cross-validation. The K -fold cross-validation method begins by randomly partitioning the dataset into k equally sized sets. Then the prediction for each sample i is calculated from a model fitted to the set $\{d - k : i \in k\}$, which is the dataset d excluding the set k where k includes i .

$$Err^K = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - f^{\{d-k:i \in k\}}(x_i)| \quad (5)$$

When $k = n$ then we produce a special form of K -fold cross-validation called the jackknife (or: leave-one-out, n -fold) cross-validation.

3.4 Bootstrap cross-validation

Bootstrapping³ is based upon a set B of bootstrap sample datasets b , for which b is of size n and is generated by randomly sampling with replacement from the full dataset d . The model is iteratively fitted to each b and prediction errors calculated for all samples i in the test set $\{d - b\}$ that consists of the dataset d with all the i in the bootstrap sample b removed. This results in around 0.632 of the dataset d occurring at least once in the training set b , and the remaining 0.368 of d occurring in testing set⁴. The estimated prediction error rate is then the mean prediction error across all bootstrap samples^{5,6}.

$$Err^B = \frac{\sum_{b=1}^B \sum_{i \in \{d-b\}} |y_i - f^{(b)}(x_i)|}{\sum_{b=1}^B \#\{d-b\}} \quad (6)$$

It is worth noting in the context of a replication study that the equation used to calculate Err^B was later changed, as this caused some confusion during our replication. The second equation⁷ works through each sample i , and calculates the mean prediction error for a set C_i of size $\#C_i$ that is equal to the all bootstrap samples that do not contain i , $C_i = \{b \in B : i \notin b\}$.

$$Err^B = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\#C_i} \sum_{b \in C_i} |y_i - f^{(b)}(x_i)| \quad (7)$$

This second definition was later termed the ‘leave-one-out bootstrap’ where it was also noted by Efron⁸ that these “two definitions agree as $B \rightarrow \infty$ and produced nearly the same results in our simulations” which were based on $B = 50$. Although the later definition of Err^B has become more commonly used⁴, as the two methods produce nearly identical results, we have used the original definition (Equation 6) in our replication as it is simpler to compute, and was the version used by Verbyla and Litvaitis¹ that we are trying to replicate.

4 Computational experiment replication

Verbyla and Litvaitis¹ based their computational experiment on applying linear discriminant analysis models to a random dataset. Their premise was that by creating a random dataset the predictive ability of a model should be no better than chance, and hence as the true prediction error was known exactly each resampling method could be assessed for bias and precision.

4.1 Random datasets

Each of 1000 computational experiments began by creating a random dataset. The response variable consisted of 30 observations that were randomly assigned a presence = 1 or absence = 0 value. These 30 observations were then matched with 10 explanatory variables. Verbyla and Litvaitis¹ state that the “ten predictor variables were generated with univariate normal distributions and equal variances” but neither the mean nor variance used was reported. Therefore, we assumed a standard normal distribution of $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma = 1$. For each random dataset a linear discriminant analysis model was fitted and prediction error calculated using each resampling method.

4.2 Resubstitution

The resubstitution method is the simplest approach and the most consistently reported in the literature, therefore we applied the methodology exactly as described.

4.3 K -fold cross-validation)

We conducted K -fold cross-validation with $K = 10$ and $K = n$ as in Verbyla and Litvaitis¹ – remembering that $K = n$ is equivalent to the jackknife method. We also included $K = 3$ as this represents a situation with a similar proportion of the dataset forming training and testing sets as with the bootstrap. This was done to assess if the proportion of data within training and testing sets was affecting comparisons of the resampling methods.

4.4 Bootstrap cross-validation

The bootstrap method was applied with bootstrap samples $B = 200$ as specified in the example code provided by Verbyla and Litvaitis¹.

4.5 Hold-out cross-validation

We included three cases of hold-out cross-validation as while Verbyla and Litvaitis¹ stated that for this method the “the estimate of model classification accuracy will not be very precise” no experiments or citations were provided to support this claim. In addition we felt there was some inconsistency in the two citations given with reference to this method. While Verbyla and Litvaitis¹ state “only one estimate of accuracy is made” which matches the citation⁹ using hold-out cross-validation with $H = 1$, a second citation¹⁰ referred to hold-out cross-validation with $H = 10$. Given this uncertainty we explored three different versions of hold-out cross-validation. We used $p = 0.368$ twice to match the proportion of test data in the bootstrap approach, and with $H = 1$ for one method, and $H = 200$ in the second method for consistency with the bootstrap. We also used $H = 200$ with $p = 0.200$ to examine sensitivity to the test data proportion.

5 Results

The results for each resampling method were presented by Verbyla and Litvaitis¹ as a “smoothed frequency distribution” but the smoothing method was not reported. As their results appeared to be normally distributed, to mimic the original results to aid comparisons we produced our smoothed distributions using a one-dimensional Gaussian kernel density estimator with a bandwidth of one (Figure 1).

Looking at the distribution of Err across the 1000 computational experiments, the resubstitution method produced clearly biased estimates of prediction error. All the other

Figure 1. Smoothed distributions of estimates of prediction error for various resampling methods from 1000 computational experiments with the known prediction error of 0.5 also marked.

methods produced unbiased estimates, but there was notable variation in the precision of those estimates, with $Err^{B=200}$ ($\mu = 0.497$, $\sigma = 0.069$) producing the most precise estimates.

6 Conclusion

While a lack of method description means our implementation will be different to that of Verbyla and Litvaitis¹, we would conclude that our results are sufficiently similar to have replicated their computational experiments.

Our findings confirm that resubstitution is a biased estimate of prediction error, and that bootstrap cross-validation produces the most precise unbiased estimate. We also found that hold-out cross-validation produced unbiased but highly variable estimates of Err as the method is clearly sensitive to the choice of parameters. We found little difference between any of the K -fold cross-validation methods.

Given the findings from our replication, we would support Verbyla and Litvaitis¹ in advocating the use of the bootstrap, as it produced the most precise estimate, and unlike other resampling methods it does not require an arbitrary choice of dataset partitions or splits that could confound inter-study comparisons of model evaluations.

We conclude that while not a substitute for truly independent data, resampling methods should be considered an important part of species-environment relationship model evaluation, and would encourage the use of the bootstrap cross-validation method in particular.

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